

Supporting Information

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The change from Conventional Thermal Processing (CTP) to Rapid Thermal Processing (RTP) is not obvious at all since the system becomes kinetically controlled and the CZTSe formation mechanism can drastically change. In this work we present the transfer of our kesterite production baseline (Cu₂ZnSnSe₄: Ge) from CTP using a tubular furnace, towards a RTP process by studying the formation mechanisms as well as photovoltaic absorber properties.

S1. SEM

Figure S1. a) Cross Sectional image of a Kesterite Precursor obtained via Sputtering. b) Cross Sectional Image of a Kesterite Absorber obtained via RTP.

S2.

S4.

Figure S4. Raman analysis of the different samples produced in the break off experiment using 4 different excitation wavelengths (325 nm, 442 nm, 532 nm and 785 nm)

Figure S4 shows the Raman spectra obtained in the different samples for the four different wavelengths. In particular under UV excitation (325 nm) the ZnO phase. Under blue excitation (442 nm) the ZnSe is enhanced and with red excitation we are able to detect Sn-Se and quaternary

S5.

Figure S5. Sodium depth profile evolution through RTP processing

In FigureS5, the sodium depth profile evolution is shown. It can be observed that the typical sodium segregation at the interfaces (CZTSe/Mo and CZTSe/air) increases with increasing process steps. Sample H shows a sodium profile out of trend, probably due to an anomalous sodium content in the glass substrate.

S6.

Figure S6. Comparison of Cu, Zn, Sn and Se depth profiles in different samples, measured after different RTP step processes

In Figure S6 the elements' depth profiles in samples F, G, H and I are reported. Similar compositions and homogeneous elements distribution are found in all the samples, showing that a thermal treatment of 5 minutes at 400 °C (sample F) is enough to obtain a homogeneous sample, despite the precursor is a metallic stack. This finding points out a very fast reaction kinetic (that could involve a liquid phase).

Other significant effects are the widening of the selenium depth profile, probably due to the molybdenum selenization, and the increasing of a shoulder in the Cu profile that should arise from a copper diffusion inside the molybdenum. It is also visible a change in the surface element distribution: while the Se content at the surface seems almost constant during the process (after the step 2), Cu and Zn concentration seem to increase whereas an opposite trend is found for Sn.